

The Thermal Decomposition of Oxyhyponitrites of Barium and Potassium

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Barium and potassium oxyhyponitrites are found to behave exactly alike and like the sodium salt : nitrogen(I) oxide is the main gaseous product in all the three cases. No nitric oxide is produced except if the nitrite produced decomposes. Nitrate is formed though no nitric oxide is present in the products.

THE preparation and decomposition of oxyhyponitrites of sodium, calcium, barium, strontium, and lead is very sparsely reported^{1,2}. The sodium salt is stated to decompose as $2\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2 + 2\text{NaNO}_2$ (1) followed by $3\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{Na}_2\text{O} + 2\text{NaNO}_2 + 2\text{N}_2$ (2) and all the rest as $\text{M}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{M}_2\text{O} + 2\text{NO}$ (3). The sodium salt reported by Oza³ and by Oza and Dipali⁴ decomposed as $2\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow 2\text{NaNO}_2 + \text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{N}_2\text{O}$ (4).

The theory of decomposition of hyponitrites⁵, of oxynitrogen salts⁴ and mode of linkage of oxygen in these oxy-salts⁶ need studies on these salts. Quantitative similarity in the behaviour of sodium hyponitrite and oxyhyponitrite is reported in Oza and Dipali⁴. It now emerges that the oxy-salts of sodium, potassium and barium behave identically and *not* differently as reported earlier.¹

Experimental

Technique of work was the same⁴. Heating was done ultimately till cessation of gas evolution to ensure decomposition of all hyponitrite and oxyhyponitrite. Barium and potassium salts were prepared by double decomposition using the sodium salt; both were monohydrates.¹ Found : K, 45.95 ; N (Dumas) 16.28 ; Ba, 59.29 ; N, 12.10%. $\text{K}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires K, 45.35; N, 16.30; $\text{BaN}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ba, 59.31 ; N, 12.12%. Nitrogen(I)oxide was first absorbed out in cold alcohol satd. with nitric oxide and residual gas tested for presence of nitrogen(II)oxide with satd. FeSO_4 soln. K_2O was removed from the solid residue by shaking repeatedly with alcohol and the material left dissolved in water. The residue of barium salt was dissolved in water ; the addition of AgNO_3 aq. to this indicated presence of traces of hyponitrite. Oxide was titrated with succinic acid, nitrite with permanganate and total nitrate as in ref. 7. The traces of hyponitrite present were removed prior to estimation by boiling⁹ since nitrites are stable in such solutions⁸.

Results and Discussion

The table shows results obtained when weighed amounts were decomposed in vacuo at temperatures stated. The gas stated under (b) was obtained at the higher temperature until gas evolution ceased. Results 1-10 for barium salt and 11-23 for potassium salt, being similar, are reviewed collectively. Except at 550° no nitrogen(II)oxide is present: the presence of oxygen confirms this (Exp. 23). Note that oxygen is evolved first and nitric oxide next. Nitrogen(I)oxide is the major gas while oxide and nitrite major solid products. When abruptly decomposed, production of nitrogen and nitrate increases. The amounts of nitrite and oxide produced do not bear relation to the amount of oxy-salt decomposed (Exps. 1-4) but the ratios (a) oxide formed to oxy-salt decomposed, (b) nitrite formed to oxy-salt decomposed are approximately constant.

Evidently nitrogen(II)oxide is not a product: so eq.(1) is dismissed.¹ Oxygen is evolved first and nitrogen(II)oxide next: intermediate peroxide formation is favoured⁸. The formation of nitrogen(I)oxide and nitrite—major products—is also readily explained on intermediate production of metal peroxide. Thus—

Oxygen is formed from M_2O_2 (I) while NO from MNO_2 (II), the latter only when temperature is suitably high.

The disproportionation reaction of Angeli¹⁰, occurring side by side with decomposition, explains the production of nitrogen.

Metal peroxide formed in (IV) exercises cheque on

TABLE—THE THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF BARIUM OXYHYPONITRITE AND POTASSIUM OXYHYPONITRITE

Exp. No.	Mass (mg)	Time (mt)	Temp. °C	Lot No.	Gas(ml)					NO ₂ N ₂ O ₅	Solid residue(mg.)			Ratios	
					Total	NO	N ₂ O	O ₂	N ₂		Oxide	Nitrite	Nitrate	BaO BaN ₂ O ₅	Ba(NO ₃) ₂ BaN ₂ O ₆
1	25.00	—	255		1.2	nil	0.65 (53.8)	nil	0.55	nil	6.1	13.8	2.00	0.27	0.60
2	50.60	—	"		2.9	"	2.0 (70.0)	"	0.90	"	12.8	27.5	3.0	0.28	0.60
3	75.00	—	"	a	1.8	"	1.4 (77.7)	0.1	0.30	"					
			350	b	2.4	"	1.6 (66.6)	0.15	0.65	"	20.3	38.5	5.6	0.30	0.56
4	150.00	—	255-350		7.9	"	4.2 (54.0)	0.1	3.6	"	40.5	65.4	26.00	0.29	0.47
5	250.00	—	255	a	2.7	"	2.00 (66.0)	nil	0.7	"					
			255	a	2.2	"	1.4 (68.6)	"	0.8	"					
			255	a	4.1	"	1.8 (44.0)	"	2.3	"					
			255	a	3.6	"	1.5 (41.2)	"	2.1	"					
6	300.00	—	350	b	0.2	"	0.08	"	0.12	"	66.2	111.8	39.00	0.29	0.48
			255	a	4.2	"	3.2 (76.2)	0.15	0.85	"					
			255	a	1.8	"	1.2 (66.7)	nil	0.6	"					
			255	a	0.9	"	0.55 (61.1)	"	0.35	"					
			255	a	5.8	"	3.0 (51.7)	trace	2.8	"					
7	100.00	15	255	a	1.6	"	0.9 (56.2)	nil	0.7	"					
			350	b	3.6	"	2.8 (77.7)	trace	0.8	"					
8	100.00	30	255	a	2.6	"	2.1 (80.0)	nil	0.5	nil					
			350	b	2.7	"	2.0 (74.0)	0.2	0.5	"					
9	100.00	45	255	a	4.4	"	3.0 (69.0)	nil	1.4	"					
			350	b	0.8	"	0.55 (69.0)	"	0.25	"					
10	100.00	60	255	a	3.1	"	2.1 (71.0)	0.15	0.85	"					
			255	a	2.3	"	1.5 (65.2)	0.2	0.60	"					
			350	b	0.65	"	0.4 (61.6)	trace	0.20	"					
11	100.00	15	K ₂ N ₂ O ₅ , H ₂ O ;		260	a	2.1	nil	1.1 (52.4)	nil	1.0	nil			
			400	b	3.0	"	2.4 (80.0)	"	0.6	"	28.7	49.5	1.32	0.32	0.5
12	100.00	30	260	a	2.7	"	1.45 (53.7)	"	1.25	"					
			400	b	2.7	"	2.05 (83.3)	"	0.65	"	28.9	50.1	1.34	0.32	0.56
13	100.00	45	260	a	3.6	"	2.25 (62.5)	"	1.35	"					
			400	b	1.8	"	1.15 (63.9)	"	0.65	"	28.6	50.5	1.29	0.32	0.56
14	100.00	60	260	a	3.8	"	2.5 (67.6)	"	1.3	"					
			400	b	1.15	"	0.75 (65.2)	"	0.4	"	28.5	50.5	1.34	0.32	0.56
15	51.00	—	250	—	2.9	"	1.8 (62.1)	"	1.1	"					
16	76.20	—	240	—	4.45	"	3.2 (71.0)	"	1.25	"					

(Contd. Table)

Exp. No.	Mass (mg)	Time (mt)	Temp. °C	Lot No.	Gas(ml)					Solid residue(mg.)			Ratios		
					Total	NO	N ₂ O	O ₂	N ₂	NO ₂	N ₂ H ₄	Oxide	Nitrite	Nitrate	BaO
17	100.00	—	240	a	0.55	nil	0.40 (72.7)	nil	0.15	nil					
			240	a	3.9	„	2.4 (61.5)	„	1.5						
			400	b	1.4	„	0.7 (50.0)	„	0.7						
18	124.00	„	260	a	3.5	„	2.1 (60.0)	„	1.4						
			400	b	3.2	„	2.0 (62.5)	„	1.2						
19	150.00	„	260	a	4.4	„	2.8 (63.6)	„	1.6						
			400	b	4.1	„	2.4 (58.5)	„	1.7						
20	175.00	„	260	a	4.8	„	3.3 (68.7)	„	1.5						
			400	b	4.1	„	2.0 (48.9)	„	2.1						
21	50.7	abrupt decomp.	450	—	2.5	„	0.7 (28.0)	0.2	1.6	nil	7.2	30.4	7.5	0.15	0.65
22	100.00	„	450	—	4.85	„	1.45 (30.0)	0.2	3.2		13.8	63.1	7.7	0.15	0.70
23	172	„	550	b	4.5	„	0.1 (2.0)	0.2 (4.0)	4.2 (94.0)						
			550	b	2.9	0.2 (6.6)	0.1 (3.3)	nil	2.6 (90.1)						

the production of hyponitrite as in(III) since it will stabilize the oxy-salt, so production of nitrogen will abate after the start of the reaction, it will again abate about the end, as found, when the quantity of oxy-salt is very low.

Taking the instance of the barium salt the reactions may be represented as follows—

(a) Decomposition as—

accompanied by

(b) Disproportionation as—

Theory ratio (a) BaO/2BaN₂O₃ is 0.355, (b) Ba(NO₂)₂/2BaN₂O₃ is 0.503. Values for these, found in this work, are 0.302 and 0.55 respectively. Note that disproportionation which occurs tends to reduce (a) and increase (b) also that nitrate is always produced: this too affects the amounts of oxide and nitrate as a overall equations shown below—

The observation that nitrate is produced even when nitrogen(II)oxide—presumably oxygen carrier in such reactions—is altogether absent supports intermediate peroxide formation theory.

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